

PAU indicated PMS lines had mid-early duration (104-106 d); seed set percentage ranged from 8.2 (PMS-2 A) to 18.5% (PMS-10 A). □

Yield potential

Hormonal signals from root to shoot in xylem sap of rice plants in drying soil

A. Bano, *Biological Sciences Department, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan; and K. Dorffling, Institute of General Botany, University of Hamburg, Germany*

We compared changes in soil moisture and root water status in horizontally divided, differentially treated root systems of rice plants with changes in leaf water potential, leaf conductance, contents of free and bound abscisic acid (ABA), and cytokinins in the shoot xylem. ABA is a hormone that signals water deficit in soil and closes stomata. Cytokinins are antagonists of ABA as regards stomatal closure.

Seeds of rice cultivar IR36 were sown in sandy loam with 48% humus and raised in growth chambers. Seedlings were transplanted 3 wk after sowing in small plastic pots that fit into a Scholander chamber. We allowed roots that protruded from the bottom of the pots to grow in nutrient solution in beakers below the pots. Three weeks after transplanting, three stress treatments were started: 1) soil and protruding roots kept moist (control), 2) soil unwatered, but protruding roots kept moist, and 3) both soil and protruding roots unwatered for 30 h (water-stressed plants). Soil and protruding roots from treatment 3 were rewatered after 30 h.

Contents of free and bound ABA and cytokinins (2iP + 2iPA and t-Z + t-ZR equivalents) in xylem sap of well-watered, water-stressed, and rewatered rice seedlings.

Treatment	Free ABA (pmol/ml)	Bound ABA (pmol/ml)	2iP + 2iPA equivalent (pmol/ml)	t-Z + t-ZR equivalent (pmol/ml)
Well-watered	7.2 ± 1	73 ± 7.5	3.7	0.9
Water-stressed	92 ± 3	499 ± 75	0.8	0.2
Rewatered	52 ± 12	87 ± 5.7	1.9	0.3

Treatment 2 reduced soil moisture from 30 to 14% within 96 h, but did not alter leaf ψ_w (see figure). When soil moisture decreased below 14%, leaf and stem ψ_w sharply declined, indicating the onset of drought stress. Although the water potential of the shoot did not change when soil moisture ranged from 30 to 14%, leaf conductance decreased by about 50%. This decrease was inversely related to the content of free ABA in the xylem which was measured by radioimmunoassay. The increase of ABA in the xylem probably was root-sourced because the shoot was not drought-stressed during this phase of soil drying.

Prolonged (96-144 h) soil drying from 14 to 6% soil moisture resulted in a further decline in conductance, accompanied by a further threefold increase in ABA. At this stage the shoot was under drought stress. The additional ABA presumably was formed in the shoot and redistributed within the whole plant via phloem and xylem.

Xylem sap contained considerable amounts of bound ABA, the level of which increased during soil drying (treatment 3) and decreased again with rewatering (see table). In contrast, cytokinin levels (isopentenyladenine + isopentenyladenosine equivalents and trans-zeatin + trans-zeatinriboside equivalents [2 iP + 2iPA and t-Z + t-ZR equivalents]), measured by an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, decreased during soil drying and increased again after rewatering. As cytokinins promote stomatal opening, their quantitative change may also explain observed changes in conductance.

The results provide evidence that rice roots sense soil moisture and send ABA as a hormonal signal to the shoot, which reacts by closing the stomata, and cytokinins as a hormonal signal to open

Changes in leaf conductance, leaf and stem water potential, and xylem ABA content of rice seedlings with upper roots in drying soil and lower roots in water.

stomata. Stomatal closure in response to ABA, and possibly by other adaptive processes, occurs before shoot water deficit develops. Further studies are necessary to elucidate the mechanism of root-to-shoot communication in rice under field conditions. □

Performance of *Oryza sativa* L. varieties under upland field conditions in Papua New Guinea (PNG)

J. S. Wohuinangu, *Department of Agriculture and Livestock (DAL), Food Management Branch (FMB), P.O. Box 417, Konedobu, PNG; M. S. Sajjad, DAL, FMB, Erap Research Centre, P.O. Box 1984, Lae, PNG*

We evaluated rice genotypes Tambu (Senis/C12), Wantok (Senis/C22), Niupela (a selection from E1 from Indonesia), Senis (a selection from IR20), BR12-5-5-1-1 (developed in PNG), NG8297 (IR9728-2-2-2-2), NG8304 (IR13429-196-1-20), NG8313 (IR46), NG8315 (IR54), and NG8321 (IR4744-295-2-3) under upland field conditions during 1991 in Markham Valley, Morobe Province, PNG.